

PARENTAL AUTHORITATIVE BEHAVIOUR AS CORRELATES OF ADOLESCENT SEXUAL BEHAVIOUR AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to determine the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. One research question and one null hypothesis were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study comprised all the 112,481 secondary school students in the 297 public secondary schools in Enugu State, while the sample size for this study was 397 public secondary school students in Enugu State. The researcher used proportionate stratified random sampling technique to draw 5% of male and female secondary school students from the 297 public secondary schools in Enugu State. A self-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three research experts. The reliability coefficient stood at 0.69, indicating that the instrument is reliable and suitable for the study. The instrument was administered to the 397 respondents using direct delivery and retrieval method. However, out of the 397 administered copies of the instrument only 318 copies were correctly retrieved. Mean and standard deviation was employed in answering the research question, while t-test at 0.05 level of significance was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study. On the decision rule, real limit of the numbers was applied. The null hypothesis will not be rejected when the significant level was less than .05 and will be rejected when the significant level was equal or more than .05 level of significance. From the result of the findings, it was concluded that parental authoritative behaviour correlates with adolescents' sexual behaviour of secondary school students in Enugu State. Comparison of the male and female students indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female students on the extent to which parental authoritative behaviour correlates with adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that Parental authoritative behaviour should be encouraged and adopted for positive adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students' in Enugu State.

Keyword: Authoritative Behaviour, Adolescent, Sexual Behaviour, Secondary School Students

Introduction

The secondary school education is one aspect of educational institutions goal in Nigeria that is designed specifically to train and prepare students for middle-level services in both manufacturing and service industries. One of the objectives of secondary education according to Atuyi (2019), is the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society. It must be emphasized that secondary education in Nigeria is for six years duration, junior secondary school (3 years) and senior secondary school (3 years). The two stages are both vocational and academic in nature. The broad goal of secondary education as stated in the National Policy on Education is to prepare the individual citizen for useful living within the society and preparation for higher education (FRN, 2013). Secondary education does not only occupy an important place in the Nigeria Education System but also serves as a link between the primary and tertiary levels of education; and because of its central position, its programmes have functional roles such as giving students access to higher education as well as preparing them for work. According to Ibe (2016), secondary education provides avenue for interaction among human being with divergent needs, interest and motives. Enose (2020), summed it up by noting that educational organization such as secondary school system exists in a symbolic relationship with the environment while utilizing both human and material resources for the production of educated, socialized graduates. It is worthy to note that the secondary school level is predominantly made of adolescents who are constantly at conflict with the developmental changes they undergo which gives them the disposition of the sexual behaviour they exhibit. Thus, Adolescents' behaviour has been alleged as one of the prevailing problems affecting the standard of education in the secondary schools not only in

Nigeria but also across many nations around the world. Udoka (2016), posited that most schools are battling with one form of adolescents' sexual behaviour or the other. Udoka added that it seems the school authorities are losing the battles against adolescents' sexual behaviour as it is getting worse each passing day. Many authors (Ekpo and Ajake, 2023 & Amazu, 2016), have written on the issue of adolescents' sexual behaviour and its alarming degree of complexity and sophistication. These authors are of the view that adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students undermines the attainment of the goal of secondary education. Thus, the need to carry out this study on correlates of adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students as the gap created by it is long overdue.

Adolescence has been defined variously by many authors. According to World Health Organization (WHO) (2019), an adolescent is a young person between 10-19 years with his or her own views and evolving decision-making capacities. This is often a stage when conflict and tensions arise and adolescents become identified as problematic by parents. An adolescent is also defined by Hornby (2022), as a person growing up from childhood to adulthood (12 or 13years) with drastic changes in the social, emotional and cognitive aspects. Furthermore, an adolescent has been identified to have some inherent capacities. These capacities have been clearly outlined in Hornby's definition; covering social, emotional, and cognitive aspects. Hornby in an attempt to buttress these changes (social, emotional and cognitive changes) describes them as drastic, which clearly depicts the radical and fundamental nature of such experience and the far-reaching consequences on adolescence behaviour. Aligning to the above conceptualizations, Ufobi (2022), described an adolescent as a boy or a girl who is changing into a young man and woman between the ages of 13 and 19 years. The adolescent

is also perceived by Farlex, (2022), as a young person who has undergone puberty but who has not reached full maturity. Ncheta (2023), supported these views by defining an adolescent as a person behaving in an immature way and who is also at the period of adolescence or teenage. Ncheta, noted that the adolescent years bring about many developmental changes, not only physically but also mentally and socially.

The adolescence period is a time people are both physically mature enough to reproduce and critically analyze sexual matters cognitively. The question then arises as to whether adolescents positively or negatively view sexual matters cognitively. Thus, Winnie (2018), defined adolescence as a transitional stage of development between childhood and adulthood, representing the period of time during which a person experiences a variety of biological changes and encounters a number of emotional issues, thus, this is why this period is termed, the period of storm and stress. Ekpo and Ajake (2023), noted that most secondary school students are in the adolescent stage. They have needs and problems that arise from organic, psychological and social pressures. These pressures in turn exert influences on them, which make them exhibit behaviours that are not in consonance with societal norms leading to delinquency. Huebner, Drane and Valois (2023), posited that there are psychosocial issues that adolescents deal with during their years which include among others; adolescents' sexuality and sexual behaviour.

Sexual behaviour refers to the way and manner individuals react or conduct themselves towards everything that has to do with sexual intercourse (Nwagbo and Ubachukwu, 2022). Sexual behaviour as defined by Omeje, Ekwueme and Omeje (2023), is all sexual actions and responses related to pleasant feelings. According to Abba and Echodu (2023), sexual behaviour is an individual ability to experience or express sexual feelings. However, the definition of sexual behaviour as conceived by

Gebhard, (2019), is any activity, solitary between two persons, or in a group that induces sexual arousal. Gebhard went further to stress two major determinants of human sexual behaviours; the inherited sexual response patterns that have evolved as a means of ensuring reproduction and that are a part of each individual's genetic inheritance, and the degree of restraint or other types of influence exerted on the individual by society in the expression of his sexuality.

Sexual behaviour include conducts and activities which are intended to arouse the interest of another, such as methods used to display behaviour that will attract the partner such as foreplay, masturbation, exposure of body before the opposite sex and erotic sexual discussions and chats. Udadi (2017), opined that sexual behaviour may be leading to multiple sexual intercourses, prostitution, and abnormal sexual practice such as homosexuality, lesbianism, premarital, extramarital sexual intercourse and indiscriminate use of a condom. Udadi, also stated that sexual behaviour is a total action of adolescents, in handling their sexual impulses. From the foregoing, sexual behaviour in the context of this study is all sexual acts displayed by adolescents for sexual gratification. Study by Utobo, (2022), revealed that 76 percent of the students had heterosexual intercourse. Onuiwu and Echefuns (2024), found in their study that 17 percent of girls are sexually active and out of these, 35 percent have multiple sexual partners.

The outcome of sexual behaviours may make adolescents particularly vulnerable to sexual exploitation and high-risk behaviours. Often the outcome of this behaviour can have adverse consequences such as unplanned pregnancies (for the females) and sexually transmitted infections (Umeugokwe, 2015). In agreement with the aforementioned, Udoga (2022), commented on the rate of sexual debut among adolescents in South East Nigeria and the consequences following it which Udoga enumerated as; unintended pregnancy,

sexually transmitted disease (STD), uterine cancer and abortion which usually lead to high rates of mortality. From the foregoing, it is evident that adolescent sexual behaviour culminating in pregnancy and STI's may occur among secondary school students in Enugu State.

The indirect complications of sexual behaviour among adolescents include other negative health outcomes such as increased vulnerability to partner violence (social coercion), elevated risk of HIV/AIDS, teen pregnancy, and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs, STI). It can also result in other psychological manifestations such as emotional damage, depression and other risk behaviour such as suicide, high school dropout, low self-esteem and delinquency (Voon, 2024). Adolescents are vulnerable not only to AIDS and other sexually transmitted infections (STIs) but to the indiscriminate display of sexual behaviour. Ojim (2017), posited that adolescences' belief about sex negatively influences their moral and values of society which pose a serious threat to the future of the younger generation. This leaves one to wonder the potency of parental training on the adolescents. Therefore, parental behaviour is a factor of serious concern in this study.

Parents are one of the most important and influential elements on the lives of their children. Parents are considered as the primary shapers of their children behaviour. They have the power, ability to shape, sustain and develop their children who should interested, creative and tolerant, thorough and positively involved in the learning process and educational activities. On the other hand parents who do not involve in their childrens' educational process are also considered to be capable of repressing and destroying the motivation and ability of their children through neglect and indifference to their behaviour. Ogbu (2023), posited that a child's behaviour in school depends on how successfully the child was managed by his parents in the home environment. The home environment should be an

environment where the child learns the skills, attitudes and behaviour which could mold them into a productive and well behaved individual.

Parents have been identified to have a critical role in the task of inculcating positive (sexual) behaviours in adolescents. Egbo (2023), saw parenting as the process of raising and educating a child from birth until adulthood. Parental behaviour is defined by Ncheta (2023), as the manner by which parents raise their children which may depend on the parent's level of expectations, performance, domains, and attentiveness to rule as well as the style of discipline that the parents utilize to enforce their expectations. Maccobay and Martin (2023), asserted that parenting behaviour capture two important elements of parenting: parental responsiveness and parental demandingness. Parental responsiveness (also regarded as parental warmth or supportiveness) refers to the extent to which parents intentionally foster individuality, self-reputation and self-assertion by being attuned, supportive and acquiescent to children's special needs and demands (Baumrid, 2019). Baumrid, further stressed that parental demandingness also referred to as behavioural control which refers to the claims parents make on children to become integrated into the family, by their maturity, demands, supervision, disciplinary efforts and willingness to confront the child who disobeys. Baumrid (2019), went further to state that each of these parenting behaviour reflects different naturally occurring patterns of parental values, practices and behaviour and a distinct balance of responsiveness and demandingness. According to Aleke (2016), parental behaviour which influence adolescent's sexual behaviour include; parental authoritative behaviour.

Parental authoritative behaviour is a form of parental behaviour in which both parents and children take joint decisions after sharing their views (Nyarko, 2020). Children's sentiments have great importance for responsive parents (Mehrinejad, Rajabimoghdam & Tarsafi, 2015). Oliveira (2015),

reported that authoritative parents are always helpful for their children. They participate in their child activities irrespective of their busy schedules at job, etc. Children are psychologically attached to their parents (Spera, 2015). Parents allow their children to solve any conflict on their own. Parents' expectations are high as well as they respond to the needs of their children (Berg, 2016). Moreover, he asserted that authoritative parenting style puts responsibility on the child by permitting him/her to choose. Thus, they develop the qualities of self-discipline and cooperation. Gonzalez, Holbein, and Quilter (2022), stated that children of authoritative parents are socially skilled and achievement oriented. Children do not suffer from insecurities, low self-esteem and anxiety (Simons & Conger, 2017). Results of the study conducted by Milevsky, Schlechter, Klem, and Kehl (2018) postulated the fact that adolescents having authoritative parents are more self-confident, altruistic and contented with their lives as compared to those brought through other parenting styles. In the same way, Van, Duijvenvoorde, Zanolie, Rombouts, Raijmakers, and Crone (2018), suggested that children who are not scolded by their parents for academic failure at school could solve their problems themselves and learn well. Turkel and Tezer (2018), suggested that parents should support self-dependence among their children because such children are emotionally sound, feel confident and do not look at others in troubles. Choe, Olson, and Sameroff (2023), opined that children of authoritative parents are less antisocial, more adjusted with their class fellows and can solve their problem themselves. Exploring parental authoritative behaviour on adolescents' sexual behaviour is imperative as adolescents irresponsible sexual behaviour has become an issue of serious concern to both researchers and stake holders in education.

Several research efforts have been made in relation to parental behaviour and adolescent sexual behaviour. However, none provided a concrete

answer to the relationship between parental behaviour and adolescent sexual behaviour. Adolescents with authoritative parents showed an increase in adjustment problems and having over-authoritative parents was related to a higher risk of pregnancy (Miller, 2022). Similarly, Miller (2022), and Kirby (2024), in their separate studies, assert that parental closeness, supervision, and behavioural monitoring decreased the risk of adolescent pregnancy. Crow (2018), posited that adolescents, who perceived too much psychological control on the part of parents, were more likely to have an earlier sexual debut, however, some factors such as gender play vital role in adolescent sexual behaviour. Thus in exploring the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescent's sexual behaviour, gender is a factor of serious concern within the adolescent.

Gender is described as the biological sex of an individual in terms of being male or female. It has to do with socially expected behaviour of male and female. In Nigerian society, there are differences and inequalities in the assignment of responsibilities between women and men, activities taken, access to and control over resources as well as possession of some qualities (Adigwu, 2024). Eunice, Selpher and David (2015), stated that there is significant relationship between secondary school students' gender and their sexual behaviour in secondary school. Alhourani (2023), indicated that the male students are more likely to show sexual behaviour than the females. Manning (2024), showed that male students dispose rebellious acts than the female students. An ex-post factor design study of 100 male and 100 female high school students by Ikoyi (2023), showed that more female students (60%) displayed delinquent acts in school than males. Igbo and Ihejiene (2015), however found no significant influence of gender on student sexual behaviours. The issue of gender has gained much attention with little or no conclusion especially as regards the

adolescent's sexual behaviour in secondary schools in Enugu State.

It is worthy to note that if adequate measures are not taken to explore the predictors of adolescent's sexual behaviours in secondary schools in Enugu State, education delivery might be jeopardized. This is because no meaningful teaching and learning can occur in an environment characterized by ill-sexual behaviour. In this case, both the teachers and students will be living in fear of being harassed and abused to mention but a few. The principals' on the other hand will be unable to enforce rules and regulations that will enhance effective education delivery. This situation will scare away students from school and encourage teachers' absenteeism. When this happens, teachers' productivity will be affected and by extension, students' performance in both internal and external examinations will be adversely affected. It is therefore against this background that the researcher is motivated to carry out this research on parental authoritative behaviour as correlates of adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. This constitutes the gap that this study intends to cover.

Statement of the Problem

The incidence of teenage pregnancy, sexually transmitted infection (STIs) and HIV infections among our youth has become alarming. The fact that adolescents are in the age of high sexual drive may cause many to engage in unsafe sex, premarital sex and prostitution. Male adolescents were also reported to have had sexual experience from their early age. Research reports have shown that parents spend insufficient time with their children. Some parents would even travel to distant places, leaving the children at the mercy of nannies and guardians. Such children lack parental care and attention and may end up becoming delinquent and most often would engage in early sexual intercourse even among them. Stakeholders in education have argued on parental behaviour and its influence on adolescents' sexual behaviour in secondary schools, however no

empirical studies known to this researcher provided a concrete date to the above. It is therefore a source of worry that with increasing rate of adolescents' sexual behaviour in secondary schools little or no research has been carried out to identify the influencing factors of adolescents' sexual behaviours of secondary school students in Enugu State. It is against this background that the researcher is motivated to investigate the extent to which parental authoritative behaviour influence adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescent's sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Research Question

This research question guided the study;

1. What are the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescent's sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students on the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescent's sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Method

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. Correlational design according to Ndubisi (2023) is a research design that is aimed at establishing the relationship between two or more variables. It is a form of design in which the

researcher correlates one variable with another to determine if there is a relationship between them. The researcher while adopting the correlational research design cannot manipulate any variable but gathers her information through observation, questionnaire or test. This research design was chosen because it provides the researcher the opportunity of sampling the opinions of a large number of the population considered significant to determining parental behaviour as correlates of adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. The population for the study comprised all the 112,481 secondary school students in the 295 public secondary schools in Enugu State. The population was made up of 37,493 male and 74,988 female students in all the public secondary schools in Enugu State. This was based on the data obtained from the Post-Primary Schools Management Board, Enugu (PPSMB, 2024/2025). The sample size for this study was 397 public secondary school students in Enugu State. The sample was made up of 175 male and 222 female secondary school students in Enugu State. The researcher used proportionate stratified random sampling technique to draw 5% of male and female secondary school students from the 295 public secondary schools in Enugu State. First, the researcher got the total population of 37,493 male and 78988 female students from the data collected from the PPSMB. From this the researcher drew 5% of male (175) and female (222) secondary school students, from each stratum respectively. The derived sample size was summed up to get the sample size of 397.

A self-structured questionnaire named “Parental Behaviour as Correlates of Adolescent Sexual Behaviour Scale” (PBCASBS), developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument has two sections; A and B. Section A contains the respondents’ bio- data while section B have 16 items. The instrument was on a 4-point scale with response options of Very Great Extent (VGE),

Great Extent (GE), Little Extent (LE) and Very Little Extent (VLE). Each response option has a numerical value assigned to it as follows;

Very Great Extent (VGE) = 4 points

Great Extent (GE) = 3 points

Low Extent (LE) = 2 points

Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point

In order to ensure the validity of the instrument, three draft copies of the instrument together with the research topic, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses, and the developed instrument were given to three experts. Two experts were from the Department of Guidance and Counselling while the other expert was from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, all from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. The experts were requested to assess the relevance, adequacy, suitability and comprehensiveness of the items in addressing the research questions as well as the clarity of the instruction to the respondents. The initial 9 generated items were increased to 16 items as suggested by the validators, while double barrel questions and grammatical errors were corrected as well. The validators’ comments were used to effect the constructive criticisms of the validators’ draft of the final instrument that was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering 30 copies of the questionnaire to a sample of 12 male and 18 female secondary school students from public secondary schools in Ebonyi State in a trial test to ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument. The choice of secondary school students in Ebonyi State public secondary schools was informed by the fact that both states have the same educational characteristics in terms of administration, population and environment. Thus, it served perfectly well as a similar population for the study. The respondents were assured of confidentiality of all the information they supplied. Data collected from the respondents’ responses were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate.

Cronbach Alpha was used because the instrument was administered once to the respondents and it was poly-dichotomously scored. The reliability coefficient stood at .69, indicating that the instrument is reliable and suitable for the study. The instrument was administered to the 397 respondents using direct delivery and retrieval method. The distribution of the questionnaire to the sampled students was done personally by the researcher with the help of five research assistants who were briefed by the researcher in a one-day consultative meeting on the modalities for administering and retrieving the instrument to the respondents. The use of research assistants is to facilitate the distribution and retrieval of the completed copies of questionnaire. Appointments were booked with the respondents for collection at a later date. However, out of the 397 administered copies of the instrument only 318 copies were correctly filled and retrieved.

Mean and standard deviation was employed in answering the research question that guided the study, while ANOVA at .05 level of significance

was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study. On the decision rule, real limit of the numbers was applied. Thus, the upper and lower limit of the mean was used to interpret the respondents mean scores as follows:

- Very Great Extent (VGE) — 3.50 — 4.00
- Great Extent (GE) — 2.50 — 3.49
- Low Extent (LE) — 1.50 — 2.49
- Very Low Extent (VLE) — 1.00 — 1.49

For the hypothesis, the bench mark was that if the value of the calculated t-calculated is equal to or greater than the critical t-value at .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. On the other hand, if the calculated t-value is less than the critical t-value at .05, the hypothesis was not rejected.

Result

Research Question 1

What are the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescents’ sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean Responses and Standard Deviation of the Respondents on the Correlates of Parental Authoritative Behaviour and Adolescents’ Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Enugu State.

N=318

S/N	Extent mentoring strategy assist in reducing male dropout in secondary schools include;	Male N=155		Female N=163		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	my parents are not responsive to my feelings	3.46	0.50	3.47	0.50	3.46	0.49	GE
2	my parents do not take my wishes into consideration before asking me to do something.	3.38	0.63	3.39	0.63	3.38	0.63	GE
3	my behaviour is being expressed by my parents through their behavior	3.23	0.80	3.24	0.80	3.23	0.80	GE
4	my parents usually do not encourage me to express my feelings	3.54	0.64	3.55	0.63	3.54	0.63	VGE
5	i am being encouraged to speak my mind even If it disagrees with my parents’ view.	3.08	0.73	3.07	0.73	3.08	0.73	GE
6	my parents do not encourage me to be independent	3.54	0.50	3.55	0.49	3.54	0.49	VGE
7	whenever am upset, my parents do not provide comfort for me	3.61	0.49	3.62	0.48	3.62	0.48	VGE
8	my parents do not compliment me when i do the right thing.	3.38	0.63	3.39	0.62	3.38	0.62	GE
9	my mother and father do not consider my opinion when they make plans for the family	3.15	0.87	3.16	0.85	3.16	0.86	GE
10	my parents do not encourage me to express my opinion	3.31	0.73	3.31	0.72	3.31	0.72	GE
11	my parents do not treat me as an equal member of the family.	3.46	0.50	3.46	0.49	3.46	0.50	GE

12	my parents usually educate me to be respectful to others	3.23	0.70	3.22	0.70	3.22	0.70	GE
13	my parents do not have intimate times together with me	3.38	0.49	3.39	0.49	3.38	0.49	GE
14	my parents expect me to handle my problems by myself	2.99	0.55	3.00	0.56	2.99	0.55	GE
15	i do keep secrets away from my parents	3.39	0.49	3.38	0.48	3.38	0.49	GE
16	my parents dictates all i do	3.08	0.83	3.08	0.82	3.08	0.83	GE
Cluster Mean		3.33		3.33		3.33		GE

Note: X=Mean; SD=Standard Deviation; VGE = Very Great Extent; GE = Great Extent

Data presented in the Table above shows that the overall mean response depicted very great extent. The items overall mean ranges from 2.99 to 3.46 indicating great extent which were all above cup-off point in the real limit of numbers. The standard deviation of 0.63 showed that the respondents have homogeneity in their responses to the items. The overall cluster mean of 3.33 also showed great extent. This implies that parental authoritative behaviour to a great extent correlates with

adolescents’ sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Hypothesis

H0₁

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students on the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and adolescents’ sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Analysis of Mean Response Scores of Male and Female Students on the Correlates of Parental Authoritative Behaviour and Adolescents Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Enugu State.

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male Student	155	.16	316	.88	-.05	.37	Accept H0 ₄
Female Student	163						

NS= Not Significant

The result of data analysis obtained from the t-test in Table 2 shows that the t-value at .05 level of significant and 316 degree of freedom for the items is .16 with a significant value of .88. Since the significant value of .88 is more than the .05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female students on the extent to which parental authoritative behaviour correlates with adolescents’ sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Discussion

Parental Authoritative Behaviour and Adolescents’ Sexual Behaviour

Result in research question sought to find out the correlates of parental authoritative behaviour and

adolescents sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. The findings revealed that parental authoritative behaviour to a great extent is correlated to adolescents’ sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. This finding is in consonance with Oliveira (2015), who reported that authoritative parents are always helpful for their children. The finding, however, disagree with Choe, Olson, and Sameroff (2023), who opined that children of authoritative parents are less antisocial, more adjusted with their class fellows and can solve their problem themselves. Authoritative parenting style puts responsibility on the child by permitting him/her to choose. Thus, they develop the qualities of self-discipline and cooperation. Therefore, parental authoritative behaviour should be encouraged and

adopted for positive adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students' in Enugu State.

Comparison of the male and female students showed that there is no significant difference in the mean response scores of male and female students on the extent parental authoritative behaviour correlates to adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State. This finding disagrees with Manning (2024), who asserted that male students dispose rebellious sexual acts than the female students. This finding equally disagrees with Ikoyi (2023), showed that more female students (60%) displayed delinquent acts in school than males. Being that adolescents' irresponsive sexual behaviour has become an issue of serious concern to both researchers and stake holders in education, parental authoritative behaviour should be adopted to control adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

Educational Implications of the Findings

The study holds implication for the government, as through the finding of this study the government will proffer solutions to cases of native sexual behaviour of secondary school students and strengthen her policy as it affects sexual behaviour in secondary schools in Enugu State, which has been ignored over the years. The school authorities through the result of this study they should equipped with better knowledge of adolescents' behaviour of secondary schools students so as provide solutions to managing them. The study shall form a guide to the school authorities on the best strategy to be adopted in the school environment at each given situation while dealing with students' sexual behaviour.

The study holds serious implication for guidance counsellors whom are saddled with the responsibility of resolving individual, family and social mal-adjustment issues. The study shall form a plank open which they shall base their strategies in controlling adolescents' sexual behaviour at all levels of education especially in secondary schools in Enugu State, and as well educate the parents on the right

and most suitable parenting style. The guidance counsellors are better equipped through this study with necessary data and knowledge needed in assisting parents out of parental challenges and adolescents sexual mal-adjustments. The adoptions of these practices are basically the gap that this study filled.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made.

- Parental authoritative behaviour should be encouraged and adopted for positive adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students' in Enugu State.
- Seminars on parenting style should be periodically organized in secondary schools and attended by parents to enlighten them on the need for good parenting styles for positive adolescents' sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Enugu State.

References

- Abba, E. R. & Echodu, S. L., (2023). The Roles of parenting styles and social capital in the school performance of immigrant Asian and Hispanic adolescents. *Social Science Quarterly*, 86(4),928-950. doi:10.1111/j.0038-4941.2005.00364.x
- Adigwu, G.T (2024) Assessment of strategies adopted by principals for students' conflict management in secondary school in Enugu State. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 2.(2), 26-38.
- Aleke, C.C (2016). Role of guidance counsellors in maintaining disciples in Secondary schools in Enugu East Local Government Area. Unpublished undergraduate project. *Guidance and Counselling*, Faculty of Education ESUT.
- Alhourani, L. (2023), Leadership and effectiveness of university Dean Lebanon and Egypt. A case study of gender and leadership styles. Unpublished of Capella University

- Amazu J. R. (2016). Parental authority questionnaire. *Journal of personality assessment*, 57(1), 110-119. doi: 10.1207/s15327752jpa570113
- Atuyi, P. A. (2019). Information and communication technology in Nigerian system. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3), 1-6.
- Baumrind, D. (2019). The influence of parenting style on adolescent competence and substance use. *Journal of Early Adolescent transition*. 236-309.
- Berg, B. (2016). The effects of parenting styles on a preschool aged child's social emotional development (Master's thesis) Educational Management, Faculty of Education BSU.
- Choe, D. E., Olson, S. L., & Sameroff, A. J. (2023). The interplay of externalizing problems and physical and inductive discipline during childhood. *Developmental psychology*, 49(11), 2029. Doi: 10.1037/a0032054
- Crow, S. (2018). Suicidal behaviour in adolescents: relationship to weight status, weight control behaviour, and body dissatisfaction. Google Books result. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17922538/>
- Ekpo, R., and Ajeke, M. (2013). Development of juvenile aggression and violence: Some common misconceptions and controversies. *American Psychologist* 53(2):242–259.
- Enose, E.D (2020). Principals Disciplinary Powers in Secondary Schools Administration. *Journal of Teachers and Teaching* 5(5) 123-133
- Eunice, T.I., Selpher, G. S. K., & David, J. (2015). Influence of teacher-student relationship on students' indiscipline In public secondary schools In Naivasha Sub-County, Kenya *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 21(9), 30-37.
- Farlex, M. (2022). Who is an adolescence. Ibadan, OluAkin Publishers.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2013). National Policy on Education Lagos: Federal Government Press
- Gebhard, P. H. (2019). Sexuality in cross-cultural perspective. *Human sexuality*, (pp. 121-122). American Psychiatric Association.
- Gonzalez, A. R., Holbein, M. F. D., & Quilter, S. (2022). High school students' goal orientations and their relationship to perceived parenting styles. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 27(3), 450-470.
- Hornby, G. (2022). Improving Parental Involvement. Continuum. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259444945-improving-parentalinvolvement>
- Huebner, E. S., Drane, W., & Valois, R. F. (2023). Levels and demographic correlates of adolescent life satisfaction reports. *School Psychology International*, 21(3), 281- 292. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034300213005>
- Ibe, E.C (2016). Effects of self-regulated learning strategy on secondary school students in social studies. Unpublished MSc dissertation. Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education ESUT.
- Igbo, D., & Ihejiene, L. (2015). Children's perceptions of family relationships as assessed in a doll story completion task: links to parenting, social competence, and externalizing behaviour. *Social Development*, 13, 551–569.
- Ikoyi, J.O., (2023). The Influence of dropout among female secondary school students in Gboyin Local Government Area, Unpublished B.Ed. Project, University of Ado – Ekiti, Nigeria.
- Kirby, A., (2014). Personality, social values, and marital satisfaction as predictors of parents' rearing styles. *International Journal of*

- Clinical and Health Psychology. <http://www.answer.com/Q/whataresocialvariable10/8/2023>.
- Maccobay, E. E., & Martin, J. A. (2023). Socialization in the content of the family child psychology. *Child Psychology*, 4.(4), 1-101.
- Manning, J. S. (2024). The nature and causes of indiscipline cases among public secondary school students in Thinka sub-county, Kiambu County, Kenya. *British Journal of Education*, 4(7), 55-66.
- Mehrinejad, S. A., Rajabimoghadam, S., & Tarsafi, M. (2015). The relationship between parenting styles and creativity and the predictability of creativity by parenting styles. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 205, 56-60. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.09.014
- Mehrinejad, S. A., Rajabimoghadam, S., & Tarsafi, M. (2015). The relationship between parenting styles and creativity and the predictability of creativity by parenting styles. *Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 2 (5), 46-60.
- Milevsky, A., Schlechter, M., Klem, L., & Kehl, R. (2018). Constellations of maternal and paternal parenting styles in adolescence: Congruity and well-being. *Marriage & Family Review*, 44(1), 81-98.
- Miller, T. (2022). Patterns of Condom Use among adolescents. The impacts of mother adolescents' communication. [ps://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9772860](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9772860)
- Ncheta, V. (2023). Parenting style among Adolescent in Udi LGA of Enugu State. Enugu State University of Science and technology. Unpublished M.Ed project. Enugu, Educational Management, Faculty of Education. ESUT.
- Nwagbo, C. R., & Ubachukwu, P. O. (2022). HIV/Aids: History, social implications and coping strategies. *Journal of Liberal Studies*, 9(1&2), 279-288.
- Nyarko, K. (2020). Parental school involvement: The case of Ghana. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 2(5), 378-381.
- Ogbu, M. (2023). National survey of adolescents and young Adults: sexual health knowledge, attitudes and experiences. Retrieved from <https://khn.org/morningbreakout/dr00017800/>
- Ojim, D.R (2017). Effect of Teachers Motivation on the Learners. *Education Digest* 7(1) 32-47
- Oliveira, E. L. (2015). The role of empathy and parenting style in the development of antisocial behaviours. *Crime & Delinquency*, 55(4), 586-599. doi:10.1177/0011128708321359
- Omeje, J. C., Millicent, N., Ekwueme, P., & Omeje, N. (2023). Environmental determinants of risky sexual behaviour. Retrieved from <http://www.liste.org/journals/index.php/RHS/article/viewfile/7943/7951>.
- Onuiwu, U., & Echefuna, M. (2014). Early predictors of sexual behaviour: implications for young adolescents and their parents. *Journal of perspectives on sexual and reproductive health*. 38(2):11-44.
- Simons, F.k and Conger, R. A. (2017). Quality of life in adolescence. The role of perceived control, parenting style, and social support. *Behaviour change special issue. Adolescent Health*, 17(3): 196-207.
- Spera, C. (2015). A review of the relationship among parenting practices, parenting styles, and adolescent school achievement?. *Educational Psychology Review*. 17 (12): 125-146. doi:10.1007/s10648-005-3950-1

- Türkel, Y. D., & Tezer, E. (2018). Parenting styles and learned resourcefulness of Turkish adolescents. *Adolescence*,
- Udadi, A. D. (2017). The relationship between Juvenile delinquency and family unit structure.(Master's Thesis). The Graduate College of Marshall University. Retrieved from <http://mds.marshall.edu/etd/750>
- Udoga, H. (2022). Age of sexual debut among Nigeria Adolescents. *journal of social and Human sciences*. 5(3): 30-45.
- Udoka D.C. (2016). Counselling needs of secondary school students in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State. Unpublished undergraduate project. Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, ESUT.
- Ufobi, U. (2022). Infant and young children. *International journal of education*. 2(1): 25-33.
- Umeugokwe, U. (2015). Sexually transmitted diseases information. *Integrated Journal of Education and social Science*. 1(2): 34-45.
- Utobo, N. (2022). Sexual debut among adolescent in South East Nigeria. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis: University of Ibadan. Ibadan, Oyo, Nigeria.
- Uzma,G.N. Muhammad,J., and Shehzad, F.I. (2019), relationship of parenting style with secondary school students' antisocial behaviour. In Sahiwal division. Pakpattan, Okara and Sahiwal. *International journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development* 2(2) 26-64.
- Van Duijvenvoorde, A. C., Zanolie, K., Rombouts, S. A., Raijmakers, M. E., & Crone, E. A. (2018). Evaluating the negative or valuing the positive? Neural mechanisms supporting feedbackbased learning across development. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 28(38), 9495-9503.
- Voon, V. (2024). Neutral correlates of sexual cue reactivity in individuals with and without compulsive sexual behaviour. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0102419>.
- Winnie, L. (2018). Research into the psychological well-being of young refugees. *Board of International Affairs of the Royal College of Psychiatrists* 5(3): 60-62.<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322370855-Researchinto-the-psychological-well-being-of-young>.
- World Health Organisation (WHO) (2019). Sexually transmitted infections Retrieved <http://www.who.int/topics/sexuallytransmittedinfection/en/>.